

IMPROVING UZBEKISTAN'S POSITION IN INTERNATIONAL RATINGS AND INDEXES: THEORY, PRACTICE, AND STRATEGY WITH INCLUDING EVALUATION OF ADVERTISING CAMPAIGNS ON SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS**¹Karimov Islombek Mizrobovich, ²Rakhmatullayeva Nargiza Oktyabreva**¹Master of Business Administration - Level 2²Department of "Management and Marketing" Associate Professor<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138571>

Abstract. Countries aim to raise their ranks in several worldwide rankings and indices in today's globalised world in order to strengthen their social, political, and economic status. Uzbekistan, as a rapidly developing nation in Central Asia, recognizes the importance of enhancing its reputation on the international stage. The purpose of this article is to investigate the theories, methods, and approaches needed to raise Uzbekistan's standing in global rankings and indices.

Keywords: strategy, economic indicators, social development, governance, environmental sustainability, international ratings, indexes

Аннотация. Страны стремятся повысить свои позиции в нескольких мировых рейтингах и индексах в современном глобализированном мире, чтобы укрепить свой социальный, политический и экономический статус. Узбекистан, как быстро развивающаяся страна в Центральной Азии, признает важность укрепления своей репутации на международной арене. Целью данной статьи является исследование теорий, методов и подходов, необходимых для повышения позиций Узбекистана в мировых рейтингах и индексах.

Anotatsiya. Mamlakatlar ijtimoiy, siyosiy va iqtisodiy mavqeqini mustahkamlash maqsadida bugungi globallashgan dunyoda bir nechta dunyo reytinglari va indekslarida o'z mavqeqini oshirishni maqsad qilgan. O'zbekiston Markaziy Osiyoda jadal rivojlanayotgan davlat sifatida xalqaro maydonda o'z obro'sini oshirish muhimligini tan oladi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi O'zbekistonning global reyting va indekslardagi mavqeqini oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan nazariyalar, usullar va yondashuvlarni o'rganishdan iborat.

Improving the position of Uzbekistan in international rankings and indices necessitates a multidimensional strategy centered on multiple important sectors. Increasing the nation's social progress, governance, environmental sustainability, and economic indicators are all part of this idea. Uzbekistan can improve its overall standing in numerous ratings and indices, draw in more foreign investment, and improve its reputation internationally by addressing these issues. A strategy and plan for accomplishing these objectives are provided here.:

Economic Indicators: In the Global Innovation Index 2023, Uzbekistan stayed at position 82, but it also maintained its ranking as an economy that is innovating more quickly, a distinction it first made in 2022. Encourage sustainable economic growth by developing sectors such as technology, manufacturing, and services. To encourage entrepreneurship, boost investment, and make conducting business easier, put structural reforms into place, expedite bureaucratic procedures, and enhance transparency in corporate operations. To strengthen the macroeconomic climate and draw in more foreign direct investment, increase budgetary transparency and implement banking sector reforms. Encourage innovation by offering incentives and assistance to academic institutions and local companies. **Social Development:** Uzbekistan ought to make investments in the local labour force's education, training, and skill development. As a result, a

competitive workforce with the ability to thrive in the contemporary economy will be produced. Create training programs and vocational schools that address the needs of the labor market, enhancing the skills and employability of the local workforce. Strengthen social safety nets to reduce poverty and inequality. Promote gender equality, encouraging the participation of women in economic and political spheres.

Governance: Implement anti-corruption measures to improve transparency, accountability, and rule of law. Strengthen institutions, including the judiciary, regulatory bodies, and administrative agencies, to ensure efficient and fair governance. Implementing best practices in e-governance, digitization, and public service delivery can improve public administration. Encouragement in human rights and civil liberties, fostering an environment that values freedom of speech, press, and assembly.[1]

Advertising Campaigns on Social Media Networks:

Create a powerful social media presence to connect with more people and improve opinions about Uzbekistan. Create campaigns that are specifically tailored to the interests and preferences of important markets and demographics. Highlight investment prospects, cultural heritage, tourism attractions, and success stories. [4]

Assessment of Marketing Initiatives:

Track and evaluate the results of social media initiatives for advertising.

Monitor important indicators including sentiment analysis, reach, and engagement to evaluate the campaigns' efficacy. To determine the effect of the campaigns on the target audience's opinion of Uzbekistan, gather user feedback and administer surveys. [4]

In the global SDG Index rating, Uzbekistan has increased by eight places. Uzbekistan placed 69th out of 166 nations with an index of 71.1 in the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) and worldwide experts' 2023 SDG Index rating. The following ten Sustainable Development Goals indicators showed positive progress in Uzbekistan, according to the SDG Index report for 2023:

- the country's reduction in poverty;
- encouraging wellbeing and good health;
- offering high-quality instruction;
- reaching parity between genders;
- sanitary conditions and pure water;
- infrastructure, innovation, and industrialization;
- the sustainable growth of towns and cities;
- combating global warming;
- justice, peace, and efficient government;
- cooperation for sustainable development.[2]

According to the draught presidential decree on the strategy "Uzbekistan-2030", Uzbekistan must update Improving Uzbekistan's Position in International Ratings and take reforms to a new level in order to comply with the updated constitutional and legislative framework. According to the text, all government departments and organizations would prioritise implementing the plan and achieving strategy goals. Every year, a distinct action plan will be authorised to carry out the strategy.[3]

In summary, in my point view, strengthening Uzbekistan's place in global rankings and indices necessitates a strategic approach, practical application, and theoretical comprehension.. In order to help policymakers and authorities identify the elements that impact a country's position in

various indices, theoretical understanding is essential. It entails learning the particular indications and criteria that various ratings and indexes employ as well as researching their techniques. They will be able to create focused policies and changes by concentrating on areas that require improvement thanks to this insight. But theoretical understanding on its own is insufficient. To turn the academic knowledge into concrete acts, practical application is required. This entails implementing a range of policies and changes to remedy the shortcomings found and bring them into compliance with global best practises. For instance, practical measures that can help to improve ratings and indexes include building institutions, investing in infrastructure and human resources, increasing accountability and transparency, and changing business rules. To guarantee long-term success and continuous advancement, a strategic strategy is also essential. Setting specific objectives, ranking areas that need work, and creating an all-encompassing action plan are all part of this process. In addition to taking into consideration possible obstacles and dangers, a strategic approach should take into consideration the nation's particular assets and prospects. To properly execute the plan, cooperation and coordination amongst all stakeholders including the public and commercial sectors, civic society, and foreign partners are essential. It's a complex endeavour that calls for a mix of strategic planning, practical application, and theoretical knowledge to raise Uzbekistan's status in worldwide ratings and indices. Focusing on these areas and making constant progress would help Uzbekistan become more respected internationally, draw in talent and investment, and promote long-term growth. By following these steps, Uzbekistan can gradually improve its position in international ratings and indexes, while simultaneously enhancing its reputation and attracting more investment and tourism. The incorporation of well-planned advertising campaigns on social media networks will further supplement these efforts and help create a positive global perception of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Jamshid Kuchkarov. Helena Fraser . UNITED NATIONS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT COOPERATION FRAMEWORK 2021-2025 UZBEKISTAN <https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-05/Uzbekistan-UNSDCF-2021-2025.pdf>
2. Ifoda Abdurazakova, Fotolia,Umida Axmedova, Manabu Shimoyashiro ASSESSMENT OF DEVELOPMENT RESULTS: EVALUATION OF UNDP CONTRIBUTION – UZBEKISTAN <https://www.oecd.org/countries/uzbekistan/46820458.pdf>
3. **Farrukh Khakimov**. ISSUES OF DIGITALIZATION IN THE NEW DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF UZBEKISTAN <https://strategy.uz/index.php?news=1518&lang=en>
4. Ashurova Z. O. PhD, Karimov I. M. EVALUATION OF ADVERTISING CAMPAIGNS ON SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS <https://econferenceseries.com/index.php/icmsss/article/view/2009>